

Supplementary information for “Opening the Black Box of EEBO”

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Mapping EEBO and EEBO-TCP records to the ESTC

Of the 132,846 EEBO records, 6,802 (5.12%) could not be matched to an ESTC record and will be left out of our statistical analyses. Analysis of these records indicates that they are mostly short fragments, extracts, snippets, loose pages, tracts, ballads and such, to which it has not been possible to record bibliographic metadata. Thus, the omission of these records should not bias our analyses. Conversely, 7,373 EEBO records (5.55%) were matched to more than one ESTC record. Most of these are cases where variants of an edition have been separately recorded in the ESTC as multiple entries. Such variant records may have a marginal effect on our supplemental analyses dealing with editions. However, all our main analyses operate on the work level, which is designed to map together not only variants, but also editions, and thus should not suffer from this.

Of the 60,327 EEBO-TCP records, 1,143 (1.89%) could not be matched to an ESTC record, and are therefore left out of the analysis. 3,269 EEBO-TCP records (5.42%) were matched to more than one ESTC record. The reasons for both of these are similar to those of EEBO omissions and multimappings.

In analyses comparing EEBO and EEBO-TCP to the ESTC, only ESTC records with publication years before 1700 have been included. This results in the exclusion of 4,862 (4.17%) EEBO records and 2,119 (3.41%) EEBO-TCP records that ESTC dates after this timespan. Removing these records should not have an effect in evaluating the coverage of EEBO or EEBO-TCP in terms of material before the 18th century.

Altogether, these mismatches and problems result in our final dataset being able to map 91.33% of EEBO IDs to ESTC records (121,328 out of 132,846), and 95.25% of EEBO-TCP IDs (57,461 out of 60,327). We have further verified that the remaining unmapped records hold no pattern that would affect our results.

Versions of graphs used in the article dividing the data by EEBO-TCP phase

Fig. 2

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Temporal coverage of material on the edition level

Complementing Figure 3 in the main manuscript

Fig X. Proportional coverage of material in EEBO and EEBO-TCP on the **edition** level by year, 1560 to 1700. Points denote coverage in individual years, with their sizes noting the absolute number of publications of that type each year. Lines show smoothed trends. Mean coverage for all material before 1560 shown on the left.

Utilising USTC genres to evaluate the genre coverage of EEBO and EEBO-TCP

To evaluate the coverage of EEBO and EEBO-TCP concerning genre, we have made use of the USTC genre keywords associated with EEBO. However, when evaluating and verifying these, we noticed that not all of the USTC genre allocations matched our analytical expectations. For example, the genre “History and chronicles” was applied extremely liberally, including to works that were clearly not history books, such as almanacs and proclamations (despite these also existing as genres of their own), while “Bibles” was also applied to sermons. Other genres were inconsistently tagged. For example, language and grammar books were tagged variously as “Dictionaries, vocabularies, phrasebooks, instruction in foreign languages”, “Linguistics and philology” and “Education books” in various combinations. Further, while the allocations could be used to weigh EEBO-TCP against EEBO, it did not allow weighing EEBO against the ESTC.

To overcome the latter limitation, we applied a support vector classifier to bridge the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) given to the ESTC data and the USTC genres, using the EEBO annotations as training material. In doing so, we retained only such genre associations that could be projected in a consistent and trustworthy manner. As a side effect

of this, we obtained a reliable means by which to filter the USTC genres to those applied consistently across the original data as well.

Fig X. Precision-recall curves for the USTC genre classifier using LCSH headings as features

Temporal coverage of EEBO by genre

Background graphs for the claims on how temporal coverage affects different genres.

Using projected ECCO modules

Fig X. Proportional coverage of material in EEBO on the work level by type, projected ECCO module and year, 1560 to 1700. Points denote coverage in individual years, with their sizes

noting the absolute number of publications of that type each year. Lines show smoothed trends.

Using projected USTC genres

Fig X. Proportional coverage of material in EEBO on the work level by type, projected USTC genre and year, 1560 to 1700. Points denote coverage in individual years, with their sizes noting the absolute number of publications of that type each year. Lines show smoothed trends.

Temporal coverage of EEBO-TCP by genre

Background graphs for the claims on how temporal coverage affects different genres in EEBO-TCP as a whole, as well as considering only phase I. In terms of comparing the different phases of EEBO-TCP, the overall genre balance seems about equal between Phase I and Phase II. However, when a temporal perspective is added, in many major genre categories Phase I shows a diminishing coverage toward the end of the century. But, when Phase II is added to the data, in addition to significantly improving coverage overall, this temporal bias disappears.

Temporal coverage of EEBO-TCP by genre as a whole

Using projected ECCO modules

Using projected USTC genres

Temporal coverage of EEBO-TCP Phase I only

Using projected ECCO modules

Using projected USTC genres

